

Accelerating multiscale simulations with surrogate models based on recurrent neural networks

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Simulation of Composite Materials

Coupling Scales

RNN

Learning Plastic Behaviour

Learning Damaged Behaviour

Summary and Future Work

Microscale
 $\sim 10^{-6} m$

Mesoscale
 $\sim 10^{-2} m$

Macroscale
 $\sim 10^1 - 10^2 m$

LLorca, J., González, C., Molina-Aldareguía, J.M., Segurado, J., Seltzer, R., Sket, F., Rodríguez, M., Sádaba, S., Muñoz, R. and Canal, L.P. (2011), Multiscale Modeling of Composite Materials: a Roadmap Towards Virtual Testing. *Adv. Mater.*, 23: 5130-5147.

Microscale
 $\sim 10^{-6} m$

Matrix Cracking
Fibre Breakage
Fibre Kinking
Interface Decohesion

Mesoscale
 $\sim 10^{-2} m$

Delamination

Macroscale
 $\sim 10^1 - 10^2 m$

Failure

LLorca, J., González, C., Molina-Aldareguía, J.M., Segurado, J., Seltzer, R., Sket, F., Rodríguez, M., Sádaba, S., Muñoz, R. and Canal, L.P. (2011), Multiscale Modeling of Composite Materials: a Roadmap Towards Virtual Testing. *Adv. Mater.*, 23: 5130-5147.

MULTISCALE SIMULATION STRATEGY

Constitutive models

Ply Continuum Damage Model

Ply Interface

A. H. Baluch, O. Falcó, J. L. Jiménez, B. H.A.H. Tijs, C. S. Lopes,
An efficient numerical approach to the prediction of laminate tolerance to Barely Visible Impact Damage,
Composite Structures, Volume 225, 2019

FE² - Concurrent

Computationally Expensive

Representative Volume Elements are simple

FE² - Concurrent

Elastic

$$\sigma(t_i) = f(\varepsilon(t_i))$$

Damaged Behaviour

$$\sigma(t_i) = f(\varepsilon(t_0, t_1, \dots, t_{i-1}, t_i))$$

Elastic

$$\sigma(t_i) = f(\varepsilon(t_i))$$

Damaged Behaviour

$$\sigma(t_i) = f(\varepsilon(t_0, t_1, \dots, t_{i-1}, t_i))$$

hidden state:

$$\mathbf{h}_t \in R^{h_{units} \times 1}$$

$$W_{xh} \in R^{h_{units} \times n_x}$$

$$W_{hh} \in R^{h_{units} \times h_{units}}$$

$$W_{yh} \in R^{n_y \times h_{units}}$$

$$\mathbf{h}_t = \tanh\left(W_{xh}\mathbf{x}_t + W_{hh}\mathbf{h}_{t-1}\right)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_t = W_{yh}\mathbf{h}_t$$

Initialization: $\mathbf{h}_0 = \bar{\mathbf{0}}$

Intermediate Modulus Carbon Fibres

$E_T [GPa]$	ν_T
13.00	0.40

Transversally
Isotropic

Epoxy Resin

$E [GPa]$	ν
5.07	0.35

Isotropic

Periodic Boundary Conditions

Dataset Generation. Generation of strain history paths

$N = 8$

Abaqus
(Implicit Solver)

$t \in [0,1]$

$\varepsilon \in [-0.1, 0.1]$

1000 paths

Dataset Generation. Accumulated Plastic Strain

$t = 0$

$t = 0.25$

$t = 0.5$

$t = 0.75$

$t = 1$

Dataset Generation. Effect of Fibre's Distribution

$\approx 0.66\%$

Recurrent Neural Network Architecture

- 1 Recurrent Cell : 100 hidden units
- Fully Connected Layer

~12k parameters

Mean Squared Error

$$m.s.e = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1, N} \left(\mathbf{y}_{t,i} - \bar{\mathbf{y}}_{t,i} \right)^2$$

Mean Absolute Error

$$m.a.e. = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1, N} |\mathbf{y}_{t,i} - \bar{\mathbf{y}}_{t,i}|$$

Train Set

m. s. e.	m. a. e.
0.9419	13.18

Test Set

m. s. e.	m. a. e.
1.005	13.24

Pure Elastic Behaviour

Longer History

$\varepsilon_{Y,2}$
 $\varepsilon_{Y,1}$ $V_f = 60\%$

$7 \mu m$

2
1

$60 \mu m$

$\sigma_Y [MPa]$

$\varepsilon_{X,2}$
 $\varepsilon_{X,1}$

Matrix-Fibre Interface:
Cohesive Elements

Matrix:
Plasticity
Damage

Periodic Boundary Conditions

Strain Paths:

$$t \in [0,1]$$

$$\varepsilon \in [-0.012, 0.012]$$

Damage Evolution

Tensile Damage

$t = 0$

$t = 0.05$

$t = 0.16$

$t = 0.67$

$t = 0.83$

- A methodology for training surrogate models for RVEs is tested on a micro-scale composite material RVE with matrix damage and interface debonding
- The proposed method is able to reconstruct general-shape strain-stress curves under damaged conditions.

Future Work

Implementation in Abaqus

3D RVE

Geometrical Parameters(Volume Fraction, Fibre Diameter,...)

Thank you for your attention

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